

A mild and efficient synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives catalyzed by acidic ionic liquid in solvent free condition

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Abstract : Condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine and two equivalent of ketones catalyzed by acidic ionic liquid [4-(3-methylimidazolidin-1-yl)-butane-1-sulfonic acid], in absence of solvent is an efficient procedure for the synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives. Good yields, operational simplicity, solvent free media are the main advantages of the present procedure.

Keywords : 1,5-Benzodiazepines, ketones, acidic ionic liquid [4-(3-methylimidazolidin-1-yl)-butane-1-sulfonic acid], *o*-phenylenediamines.

Introduction

Benzodiazepines and their derivatives have received considerable attention because of their pharmacological properties and synthetic utilities¹. They are used as anti-anxiety, analgesic, sedative, antidepressive and hypnotic agents² and also as dyes for acrylic fibers³ and the key intermediate for the synthesis of various fused ring compounds such as triazolo-⁴ and oxadiazolo-benzodiazepines⁵. Synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines is usually carried out by the acid-catalyzed reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine with ketones, β -haloketones and α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds. Several methods are available in the literature such as $\text{BF}_3\text{-OEt}_2$ ⁶, NaBH_4 ⁷, polyphosphoric acid- SiO_2 ⁸, ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)⁹, MgO/POCl_3 ¹⁰, $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ ¹¹, amberlyst-15 in ionic liquid¹², $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH/MW}$ ¹³, $[\text{dbim}]\text{Br}$ ¹⁴, $\text{Ag}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ ¹⁵, clinoptilolite¹⁶, molecular iodine¹⁷, $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{poly-4-vinylpyridine}$ ¹⁸, InCl_3 ¹⁹, $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ ²⁰, AgNO_3 ²¹, zeolites²², $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ ²³, $\text{HBF}_4\text{-SiO}_2$ ²⁴ and Me_2SBrBr ²⁵, $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$ ²⁶, sulfanilic acid²⁷, polyanilinesulphate (PAS)²⁸, tungstophosphoric acid on silica²⁹, NbCl_5 ³⁰ and L-proline³¹. Though these synthetic procedures are useful in many cases, a number of them show disadvantages like long reaction times, expensive reagents, use of large amounts of hazardous and toxic solvents, poor yields of the products, drastic reaction conditions, tedious work-up procedure and occurrence of several side products. So a more general, economical and

environmentally safer methodology is desirable for the synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines.

Results and discussion

In continuing our effort to develop new synthetic methodologies³², using IL as catalysis and solvent herein, we report a mild and efficient condensation reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and ketones under mild conditions. In a typical general procedure, a mixture diamine and ketone in presence of 8 mol% of the acidic ionic liquid 4-(3-methylimidazolidin-1-yl)butane-1-sulfonic acid was heated at 60–70 °C for two hours (Scheme 1). A wide range of structurally diverse ketones underwent reaction by this procedure to provide 1,5-benzodiazepines in moderate to good yields. The results are summarized in Table 1. As evident from the results, this procedure is uniformly effective for aliphatic, cyclic and aromatic ketones. The reaction time is two hours for aliphatic, cyclic as well as aromatic ketones. Aromatic ketones with both activating and deactivating groups such as Me, OH and Cl reacted to afford the corresponding products almost in equal time and in comparable yields. The reaction has been carried out at different temperature from 60 °C to 100 °C, but at temperature less than 60 °C the yields are very poor (30–40%). When the reaction was carried out at about 100 °C and higher temperature a mixture of products were isolated which were very difficult to sepa-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Preparation of 1,5-benzodiazepines (3), starting from *o*-phenylenediamine (1)

Entry	Ketone (2)	Product (3)	Yield (%) ^a	M.p. (°C)
1			81	137-139 138-140 ²¹
2			60	144-145 143-144 ²⁷
3			76	137-138 137-139 ²⁷
4			60	117-118 118-119 ³³
5			60	138-139 138-140 ²¹
6			60	139-140 138-140 ²¹
7			75	151-152 150-152 ²¹
8			60	b
9			75	142-143 143-144 ²³

Table-1 (contd.)

10		60	150-151 ³³ 149-150
11		78	160-161 160-163 ²⁷

^aYields are pure isolated products. ^bThis compound is gummy solid.

rate and characterize. No organic or aqueous solvents were used in the reaction only ethyl acetate was used for isolation of the product from the reaction mixture and ethyl acetate-hexane mixture was employed for recrystallization to provide analytically pure samples.

In conclusion, we developed a very simple and efficient methodology for the preparation of 1,5-benzodiazepines with moderate to good yields. Operational simplicity, reaction in solvent free media, mild reaction conditions, environment friendly nature and the compatibility with various functional groups are the important advantages of the present procedure.

Experimental

A mixture diamine (1) (1 mmol, 108 mg) and methyl ethyl ketone (entry 3) (2.5 mmol, 108 mg) was taken in presence of acidic ionic liquid [4-(3-methylimidazolidin-1-yl)-butane-1-sulfonic acid] (8 mol%, 25 mg) was stirred at 60-70 °C for two hours. After completion of the reaction (TLC) the reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated under reduced pressure to furnish the crude product. The crude product was

purified by column chromatography on silica gel to get the pure product in 76% yield (164 mg). All the compounds were characterized by comparison with standard literature data like m.p. and spectral data.

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